

ENA Interactive Data Submission Practical

As we have discussed, there are three routes of submission:

- Interactive
- Programmatic
- Webin-CLI

In this exercise, you will have the opportunity to submit a set of raw read data to the test version of the **ENA Interactive Submission** service.

Webin Submissions Portal (TEST): <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

You will need an ENA Webin account to use for this exercise. Webin accounts can be registered on the webin portal 'Register' page:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/accountInfo>

The screenshot shows the 'Webin Submissions Portal' registration page. At the top, there is a header with the ENA logo and the text 'EUROPEAN GENOME-PHENOME ARCHIVE Webin Submissions Portal'. Below the header, the page is titled 'Account Management'. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column is titled 'Account Details' and contains five input fields: 'Abbreviated center name', 'Full center name', 'Laboratory Name', 'Address', and 'Country'. The right column contains two input fields: 'Password' and 'Confirm Password'. Below the input fields, there is a section titled 'Contact Information' with a sub-header 'Add At Least One Contact' and a plus sign icon. At the bottom of the form, there is a section titled 'No Sensitive Data' with a checkbox and the text 'I confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable.'

It will be helpful to review how the metadata model works. You can find an overview of this here:

[Metadata Model](#)

Throughout this exercise, you are asked to use the ENA test service, which allows you to make submissions which will be removed after 24 hours. If you're not sure if you're in the test server, you can check the address in your browser which will begin 'wwwdev' rather than 'www':

 <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

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The Scenario

You will be submitting a set of paired read data files derived from mouse gut metagenome to the ENA test submission service. This is identical to the production submission service, but submissions are retained for <24 hours. It's therefore perfect for training settings like this.

The Study

To begin, you should **register a study**. Recall that a study describes the purpose of the work you have done, groups other objects beneath it, and controls when the data becomes public. A study is required for all submissions to ENA.

1. Log in to the Webin test submission service with your account ID and the password:
<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/>
2. After logging in, find the 'Studies (Projects)' tab and click on the '**Register study (project)**' button to see the study registration interface:

3. Set a **release date** for your study (this is when all data associated with the study will be released). This needs to be between now and a maximum of 2 years in the future.
4. The '**Study Name**' field should be filled in with something brief and meaningful that can help you find and recognise the study.
5. You should take time to provide a descriptive title and informative abstract for your own studies, but these can be edited later if needed. The title could be something similar to:
Study of Mouse Gut Microbiome from <Your Town/Lab>
6. When you have completed all required fields, click '**Submit**' and then confirm.
7. Now back on the main page, navigate to the 'Studies (Projects)' tab and click on the '**Studies Report**' button to see the study you just registered. You might need to refresh the page.
Make a note of its accession numbers, which will resemble:

ERP##### and PRJEB#####

Note: For a real submission, these would be the numbers you would cite in any publications involving the data.

The Sample

The next step is to register the sample, which will give other users essential context for the sequence data you are submitting. The sample describes the source biological material of your sequencing work.

In ENA, samples are required to conform to a checklist of values. Checklists define a set of mandatory and recommended values for a given type of sample. It is recommended that you look at these early and make sure you collect all required metadata items for the type of sample you will be registering.

The selection of available checklists can be browsed at:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/checklists>

1. Return to the main page of the Webin Portal and find the 'Samples' tab.

<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/>

2. Click on the '**Register samples**' button.
3. Expand the section '**Download spreadsheet to register samples**'. You must choose an appropriate checklist of values to be provided for your sample. Browse the range of checklists available.

Note: Please make sure you use a MlxS checklist (Environmental checklist) for metagenomic data.

4. Which samples checklist do you feel is most relevant for the sample you have sequenced?

You can read the descriptions of the metadata fields on the [browser checklists page](#).

5. Submitters now have the option of including additional fields in their checklist. It is not necessary to include any additional fields but you can take this opportunity to see which fields are included as mandatory, recommended and optional, what requirements they have, and what else is available.

Click '**Next**' when you're ready.

6. Download the TSV template and open the file in Excel on your computer.

Please note that you should submit your spreadsheet in the same format that you have downloaded it (TSV).

7. When you open the TSV template, the 3rd row will state “#units”. Please keep this row intact and enter your data from the 4th row as shown below. This is important for the system to successfully parse your tsv file:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
1	Checklist	ERC00001												
2	tax_id	scientific_name	sample_alias	sample_title	sample_description	project na	collection	geographi	geographi	geographi	broad-sca	local enviro	environmental	medium
3	#units								DD	DD				
4		1 mouse gut metagenome	text											
5														

8. Find the appropriate taxon for your sample: to reiterate what we discussed during the presentation, please use a taxonomy that is as specific as possible. In this case for example, “**mouse gut metagenome**” instead of “**mus musculus**”.

- a. This can be looked up on our rest API. Here is an example of a search of “metagenome”:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/taxonomy/rest/scientific-name/metagenome>

You can also search for the species name to find its tax ID on the NCBI Taxonomy database.

- b. NCBI Taxonomy database:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>

9. Give a 'Unique name' to your sample (sample_alias)

This value must always be unique among all samples submitted by your account and is a way for you to locate and recognise your specific samples.

10. Give your sample a title, this could look something like:

Mouse gut sample from <Your Town/Lab/Location>.

11. Write a brief description for your sample

12. Fill out the remaining details.

Tip: You can always find out more about what a field means and what information it accepts by going back to the checklist fields page on the Webin Portal and reading their description and validation.

Collection date format (year-month-date): 2024-10-24 , 2024-10 , 2024

13. By the time you have completed this, your sample will be well-annotated and understandable to people finding it in the database later. Click on ‘**Upload filled**

spreadsheet to register samples' on the Register Samples page and upload/submit the spreadsheet.

14. Now back on the main page, navigate to the 'Samples' tab to see the sample you just registered. You might need to refresh the page.
Make a note of its accession numbers as you will need these later.

ERS#####

The Read Data

Now that study and sample metadata have been registered, it is time to upload and submit the read data you have produced.

In this scenario, let's say you have sequenced your sample and produced a set of paired read data files.

- file_R1.fastq.gz
- file_R2.fastq.gz

These are the raw read data files you have obtained as a result of sequencing your sample and comprise of a forward reads file and a reverse reads file.

Uploading Data Files

Before submitting the read data files, you must upload them. All Webin submission accounts come with a space on our server to upload files to. In most cases, submitters must upload their files to this before they are able to submit.

You will upload files to your private Webin file upload area using either FTP or Aspera protocol through the webin2.ebi.ac.uk service. The authentication is done using your Webin submission account name and password.

1. There are a number of tools and ways to accomplish the upload. For the purpose of this workshop, we will be using FileZilla to upload your read data files. Please install FileZilla client from here: <https://filezilla-project.org/>
2. Open the tool and enter the following details at the top before clicking "Quickconnect":

Host: webin2.ebi.ac.uk
Username: Webin-xxxx
Password: xxxx

3. Once it successfully establishes a connection, you have your local computer paths and files in the windows on the left, and the remote webin upload site on the right. Find the directory with the downloaded paired fastq files and drag the files into the directory listing at the remote site. This will upload your files to your webin upload area.

Submit Data Files

- Now that the read files have been uploaded, they are ready for submission. Unsubmitted read files remain in the upload area for 3 months after which they are automatically removed if not submitted.
- Return to the main page of the Webin Portal and find the “Raw Reads (Experiments and Runs)” tab.

<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/>

- Click on the ‘**Submit Reads**’ button.
- Next, you have to select the correct read submission checklist for your data type. Expand the section ‘**Download spreadsheet template for Read submission**’.
- Now, select ‘**Submit PAIRED reads using fastq files**’ from the list of file options. Since your mouse gut data is a set of paired fastq files with forward and reverse reads instead of a single end fastq file, you will use the ‘paired reads’ template.
- View the mandatory and optional fields available for this checklist. Click ‘Next’ and download the spreadsheet.
- Fill out the spreadsheet to describe your experiments and register the files. When you are about to download your read submission checklist, you should be able to see the checklist fields and the accepted terms for the fields that do not allow free text. Have a look at the permitted values and select the fields that are correct for your experiment to input into the spreadsheet.

Sample : enter the sample accession here* (ERSxxx)

Study : enter the study accession here* (PRJEBxxx)

Instrument Model : Check permitted values

Library Name : your lab initials_sequence_library_1

Library Source : Check permitted values

Library Selection : Check permitted values

Library Strategy : Check permitted values

Library Layout : PAIRED

Forward File Name : file_R1.fastq.gz

File Md5 : [Calculate md5 checksum value](#)

Reverse File Name : file_R2.fastq.gz

File Md5 : [Calculate md5 checksum value](#)

*If you did not note down your sample accession, you can safely visit the '**Samples Report**' tab in the Webin Portal, copy the sample accession and paste it onto the spreadsheet.

8. Once complete, save the spreadsheet in the same TSV format and expand the '**Upload filled spreadsheet template for Read submission**' section and upload the spreadsheet. Click '**Submit**' and see if your submission validates successfully.

Please note that you should submit your spreadsheet in the same format that you have downloaded it (TSV).

9. When you manage to complete your submission, visit the 'Runs' tab to review your submission.